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Optimized data management with color multiplexing in QR codes

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Abstract

This study integrates colorimetry and computation by identifying their commonalities to develop a novel encryption system centered around color, specifically using QR codes. We propose an approach that multiplexes QR codes of varying colors, each containing distinct information. A key is generated to encapsulate user-specific data and identify the QR code with authentic information. We develop serverless architectures to facilitate rapid encryption and decryption processes. The system's performance and efficiency are evaluated through two architectures: a sequential system implemented on Google Colab and a distributed system utilizing AWS Lambda serverless architecture. Metrics such as NPCR (Number of Pixels Change Rate), UACI (Unified Average Changing Intensity) and key space analysis, indicative of the system's robustness, are analyzed according to existing literature. In addition, the cost of this serverless technology is evaluated in comparison to cloud and local. Our findings demonstrate that the serverless architecture offers a viable and efficient solution for coding. The implications of this research extend across various sectors, including defense, healthcare, and everyday digital interactions, presenting a scalable and secure alternative for data encryption and communication.

1. Introduction

Modern encryption systems [1] protect against a diverse range of security threats. Despite significant technological advancements, substantial security challenges persist. Cryptography, the practice of converting information into an unreadable format, is essential for maintaining confidentiality. This well-established field ensures that valuable data remains inaccessible, unaltered, and undisrupted, except by the intended recipient.

Digital images and QR codes [2] are particularly effective for transmitting information over networks due to their efficient communication capabilities and high transmission rates. Encrypting these formats is crucial to safeguarding them from unauthorized access and interception during transmission. This is especially important in fields like defense and medicine, where images and QR codes often contain sensitive and private information. However, encryption of QR codes is also vital in everyday contexts. To meet these needs, a variety of symmetric and asymmetric cryptographic systems have been developed. Symmetric algorithms include stream ciphers, which encrypt data bit by bit, and block ciphers, which encrypt data in fixed-size blocks. Encrypting QR codes [3] can enhance security measures, providing a robust solution for protecting digital content in various applications.

After differentiating the types of encryption, it is important to highlight how QR codes can be used to encode information. One study explores encryption techniques such as chaos-based methods, selective compression, and DNA cryptography [4], and discusses combining encryption with image compression to enhance transmission security. Other study [5] highlights the relevance of these techniques in fields like defense, medicine, and everyday life. It also examines the impact of COVID-19 [6, 7] on internet connectivity, social networking, and online education, emphasizing the increased need for secure digital communication. Specific areas of interest include searchable encryption for secure data outsourcing [8], novel data hiding schemes for encrypted images, and the use of QR codes for digital tagging and anticounterfeiting in pharmaceuticals [9]. Another research provides a broad and deep understanding of the challenges and developments in image and QR code encryption, highlighting their practical applications across various fields.

This study proposes to combine two technologies that may seem disparate but have points in common, colorimetry and computation. First we will propose an encryption system where color is the central axis, in this case of QR codes and then using computation we will create serverless structures where encryption and decryption is done in seconds. In the part of colorimetry we rely on multiplexing [10] each of the QR codes of different color and with different information each of them, then a key is generated where you have information about the user and which of them is the one that has real information. On the other hand, in the computational part we generated a serverless architecture to do this processing in seconds, where each AWS Lambda function and S3 storage play a crucial role. Combining both concepts, an optimal structure for encoding information in QR codes has been obtained.

This paper has the following structure: section 2 contextualizes a number of previous research studies and compares them with the one presented in this article, section 3 introduces the concepts used in colorimetry and computation to realize the encryption of QR codes, and then, the elements used for the realization of serverless computing. Section 4 explains the encryption process in code and serverless computing. Section 5 on the other hand, performs the experimental analysis both colorimetric and computational, for this part will be performed using histograms and CIELab coordinates in the case of colorimetric, NPCR, UACI and key space analysis to perform quantitative metrics on the security of the presented system, and on the other hand, the computational where the execution of the code in local, cloud and serverless will be compared. Finally, section 6 shows the conclusions drawn from this research.

2. Related work

In this section we will contextualize similar works where we have based our work to develop this new technology.

We have studied different works on multiplexing [11–13] QR codes, we have seen studies applied to the artistic field and the field of computing. The first article [11] talks about a modular encryption in 3 dimensions, it is done through a series of chemical reactions where a series of colors are dated, it should be noted that its decryption process is performed by fluorescence techniques. The second article [12] talks about color multiplexing for high-resolution image displays and optical encryption, they use binary and grayscale meta-images in a nonspatially multiplexed silicon metasurface, they also provide a optical key using silicon meta-atoms and the encoding and decoding process is done by the light polarization. The third article [13] talks about a novel color QR code that combines multiple types of identification information, using multiplexing and color-coding technology to present both public and hidden information. It elaborates on the basic principles, constructs a mathematical model, and provides an algorithm design process to overcome halftone printout challenges. Our work shows an alternative in terms of security by taking advantage of the characteristics of color and serverless technology to perform the encryption, for this purpose a series of keys, it is a security alternative to the items mentioned above [11–13], and as mentioned, the serverless technology allows performing this encryption and decryption process in a faster way and is shown as an alternative for the encryption of information.

On the other hand, different uses of serverless computing have also been studied. Our technology brings a new use case to this area. The article [14] discusses a serverless solution for RNA-Seq data analysis, focusing on the mapping/alignment of sequencing reads to a reference genome, which is the most computationally intensive step. Using an in-house serverless environment, tests were conducted on 16 paired-end sequencing samples with the Ensembl GRCh38 reference genome. Results show that while serverless solutions are advantageous for highly parallel computations or numerous independent atomic operations, they are not suitable for single atomic operations requiring substantial CPU or memory resources. Other article [15] talks about a serverless computing architecture for the Emirates Mars Mission (Hope probe) to analyze images of Martian auroras, crucial for understanding the Martian atmosphere. Utilizing OpenCV and machine learning algorithms, the architecture provides efficient image classification, object detection, and segmentation. By leveraging cloud computing's scalability and elasticity, the system effectively handles large volumes of image data and adapts to

Figure 1. Three samples QR codes that can be combined used this codification.

changing workloads, offering a swift and cost-effective solution for remote sensing applications. Other article [16] presents a serverless computing architecture designed to process ionograms from the Mars Advanced Radar for Subsurface and Ionosphere Sounding (MARSIS) on Mars Express. Given the high noise levels and the sheer volume of data (>2 million ionograms), manual analysis is impractical. The serverless approach aims to detect oblique echoes, which are reflections from regions affected by crustal magnetic fields, providing critical insights into the ionosphere. This architecture is compared with two local alternatives in terms of cost and performance, demonstrating its efficiency and scalability for handling complex and variable data. The use case presents a technique where multiplexing and serverless technology are combined resulting in a new coding, where this process is done in seconds.

3. Preliminaries

To develop this coding we have relied on the use of computation and color. First we will explain the role played by color and then we will explain the reason for the use of serverless computing.

3.1. Color codification

In the development of color encryption, different techniques were considered where QR codes were combined, either in two layers or more. In addition to the techniques seen in the introduction concerning the coding of information by Fourier or other mathematical formulas.

At first it was thought to use the α value for the combination of QR codes. The following formula was used for this purpose:

$$\vec{C} = \alpha_r \times \vec{R} + \alpha_g \times \vec{G} + \alpha_b \times \vec{B} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) shows the result of the QR code result named \vec{C} , where each channel has certain alphas (α_r , α_b and α_g) [17] that influence in the three QR codes shown in figure 1. These three QR codes are shown in vector form in equation (1) (\vec{R} , \vec{G} and \vec{B}).

Once they have been mixed using this technique, a QR code is obtained where the information of the three QR codes is maintained. Figure 2 shows the result of this combination.

In an intermediate step, a function called jump function is added during this coding. This jump function can be linear (shown in equation (2)), harmonic (shown in equation (3)) or quadratic (shown in equation (4)). These function are intended to induce an error QR code.

$$f(x) = x \quad (2)$$

Then x is a fixed value which moves the message in linear way.

$$g(x) = A \cos(\omega x + \phi) \quad (3)$$

Where A is the amplitude of the function, ω is the angular frequency, x is the independent variable and ϕ is the initial phase, indicating the horizontal displacement of the function relative to the starting position.

$$h(x) = ax^2 + bx + c \quad (4)$$

Where a , b and c are constants and x is the independent variable. Giving values to these constants shifts the original message in the QR code. Figure 3 shows the intermediate step of the skip function (shown in equations (2), (3) and (4)) in the encoding process, for this image the error ones have been marked in yellow but in the use of the application all QR codes are shown as in figure 2.

3.2. Serverless architecture

On the other hand, there is serverless technology. This technology will be used in order to speed up processing at the time of coding. From this structure we will highlight the lambda functions and the S3 storage.

AWS Lambda [14] is a serverless computing service provided by Amazon Web Services (AWS) that allows developers to run code without provisioning or managing servers. The service is designed to handle compute resources automatically, scaling from a few requests per day to thousands per second, without requiring any manual intervention. Lambda functions are stateless, and they are triggered by events, making them highly suitable for event-driven architectures. The service supports several programming languages, including Python, JavaScript (Node.js), Java, C#, and Go, among others, allowing developers to use the language they are most comfortable with. Additionally, AWS Lambda integrates seamlessly with other AWS services, enhancing its capabilities and enabling complex workflows.

Lambda operates [15, 16] on a pay-as-you-go model, where users are billed based on the number of requests for their functions and the time their code executes. This model makes it cost-effective for running short-lived tasks and processing real-time data streams. Lambda also provides a high level of fault tolerance and availability, automatically replicating functions across multiple Availability Zones within a region. With built-in monitoring and logging features via AWS CloudWatch, developers can track function performance and troubleshoot issues efficiently. Lambda's event-driven model simplifies the development of scalable and resilient applications, allowing developers to focus on writing code rather than managing infrastructure. This paradigm shift has made AWS Lambda a cornerstone of modern cloud-native application development, facilitating microservices architectures and enabling rapid iteration and deployment.

Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3) is a scalable, high-speed, web-based cloud storage service designed for online backup and archiving of data and applications. S3 provides developers and IT teams with secure, durable, and highly available object storage. The service is known for its 'eleven nines' of durability, which means it is engineered to sustain the loss of data in the event of the failure of two data centers simultaneously. Data in S3 is stored in buckets, which serve as the top-level containers. Each object, which can be up to 5 terabytes in size, is stored in a bucket and identified by a unique key within the bucket. S3's simple web services interface allows for storing and retrieving any amount of data, at any time, from anywhere on the web.

S3 is designed to provide 99.99% availability, ensuring that users can reliably access their data whenever needed. The service offers multiple storage classes, including S3 Standard for frequently accessed data, S3 Intelligent-Tiering for data with unpredictable access patterns, S3 Standard-IA and S3 One Zone-IA for infrequently accessed data, and S3 Glacier and S3 Glacier Deep Archive for long-term archival. This flexibility allows users to optimize costs by choosing the appropriate storage class based on their data access patterns. S3 integrates seamlessly with other AWS services, enabling powerful workflows and analytics. For example, users can trigger AWS Lambda functions based on events in an S3 bucket or run big data analytics with Amazon Redshift Spectrum and Amazon Athena. With its robust security features, including data encryption at rest and in transit, fine-grained access controls, and compliance with numerous regulatory standards.

These two elements mentioned above have been used for the development of this coding. The AWS Lambda functions have been used to execute the code, the libraries have been transformed into the layers of the same, thus allowing the encoding of several files at the same time. Then on the other hand we have the S3 storage that has been used to launch the functions and save the results until the user downloads them from the application.

4. Codification process

Figure 4 shows the coding process that will be detailed step by step below:

- (i) **Login user in the application:** The user starts the application and then will be asked to authenticate with a username and password (shown in figure 4, first box) before starting the image upload process.
- (ii) **Codification of the image to base64:** In this step the image uploaded by the user is base64 encoded.
- (iii) **Generation of the QR Codes:** Several QR codes will be generated, one will have the image information and the others will have false information in the same format as the image, i.e. base64.
- (iv) **Generation of the key with QR characteristics:** A key will be generated with the characteristics chosen by the user for the QR code, among these characteristics is the color. At the moment the jump function is predetermined by the application. In addition, this key can only be used by the same user who has logged in.
- (v) **Multiplexed of the QR Codes:** In this phase, QR codes are combined, both those with true and false information.
- (vi) **Generate the txt file:** This reference txt has the decoding process so that the application knows in which order the QR codes go and which one contains the real information.
- (vii) **Download of the QR code and the key:** The combined QR code and its key with decoding information can be downloaded.

The decoding process is performed in reverse following the reference txt.

4.1. Key generalization

For the development of the coding by means of the keys, an encoding based on the logical operand XOR [18] (exclusive OR) has been used, where two bits of the image are obtained and it returns 1 if they are different or 0 if they are the same. To illustrate this, the following truth table will be used:

$$0 \oplus 0 = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$0 \oplus 1 = 1 \tag{6}$$

$$1 \oplus 0 = 1 \tag{7}$$

$$1 \oplus 1 = 0 \tag{8}$$

When these operands are applied, each pixel of the original image is encrypted using a secret key. Visually, the QR code looks the multiplexed but has its information encoded by a secret key which has the user.

Then for the decryption process this operand makes the operation reversible, making this process possible only by means of the user’s private key.

In addition, for this color-based coding process, a dictionary is added to this key where the user data, the chosen color and the jump function are stored. This dictionary makes the key unique for each user. By adding these jump functions, multiple codes with erroneous information are also added, so if in the case of for example, a brute force attack to the system where the attacker tries to access the information using multiple hashes and will not be able to access it so easily. On the other hand, there is another type of attack through the use of false keys, for which the generalization of the private and public key, being unique to the user, is reinforced for this type of attack.

4.2. Serverless codification process

Our first architecture, the sequential system, was implemented using Google Colab, a platform that provides a Python interactive environment with both CPU and GPU support. We leveraged Google Colab’s free access to GPU resources to accelerate the QR code generation and color multiplexing processes.

In this system, the processes of generating QR codes, color multiplexing, and encryption follow a sequential order, with each stage waiting for the previous one to complete before commencing. This ensures data consistency but could potentially result in longer processing times, particularly when dealing with large amounts of data.

The goal of our proposed system is to facilitate the generation and distribution of color multiplexed QR codes at scale. To this end, we leverage a suite of services provided by Amazon Web Services (AWS), including Lambda for serverless computing, S3 for distributed data storage, and API Gateway for triggering our system. It follows:

- (i) **Codification of the image to base64:** The file upload event to the application causes the Lambda 1 (shown in figure 5) function to be executed. This function encodes the image in base64 and saves it as input.
- (ii) **Stimate the distribution of QR Codes:** Lambda 1 (shown in figure 5) calculates the optimal distribution of the data between the QR Codes.
- (iii) **Generation of the QR Codes:** Once the distribution of information has been calculated. Lambda 2 (shown in figure 5) is in charge of generating the QR codes, both false and true information, and assigns them an identification number for the reference txt and the key.
- (iv) **Key generation:** Lambda 3 (shown in figure 5) generates a key in xml format containing information about the color, the jump function used and the maximum distribution for image decoding.
- (v) **Creation of storage in S3:** For storage, a reference txt will be used to indicate the order of the QR codes for decoding, as well as the reference color chosen. Lambda 4 (shown in figure 5) will take care of this task.

We are going to compare the cost and the processing between AWS Lambda and Google Colab. Both systems will execute the same code and will be coded and decoded the same amount of information.

5. Experimental analysis

Two factors will be taken into account for the experimental analysis: color and computation. For color, colorimetric analyses such as histogram and CIE Lab will be used to assess whether there is a decrease in resolution during encryption and decryption. In addition to quantitative values called NPCR, AUICI and key space analysis [19–21] to assess the effectiveness of the encryption algorithm. On the other hand, for the computational part, the execution of the same code in three different environments will be compared and their cost will be compared: local, cloud and serverless. For this analysis, the images of the European EyE [22, 23] project will be used.

5.1. Histograms

The histogram [5, 24] is a way to analyze both the encryption system and whether the image resolution is maintained. The encrypted image must exhibit a uniformly dispersed histogram to prevent attackers from gathering any corroborative evidence from the image histogram. On the other hand, the histograms of the original and decrypted image should be similar if the image resolution has been maintained during the encryption and decryption process.

Figure 6 shows a uniform and periodic pattern. This pattern makes it difficult for the attacker to discover what the encrypted color is, even if this was the case, the information [25] returned from the QR code would not be obtained.

For example, if an attack called a brute force [26]. This type of attack is characterized by applying different methodologies to gain access to the system. They are characterized by using a system based on trial and error, so, for the realization of this type of attacks they have to be extended in time. Based on the reasoning of similar encryption systems [27–30] where parameters similar to those shown are analyzed, it can be said that our system is a valid option due to its periodic histogram, its generalization of unique keys for each user and for allowing the user to select the color to be encrypted.

On the other hand, we will discuss how the system will act in the event of a false key attack [31]. This type of attack is characterized by the simulation of different passwords. For this type of attack, different password generation programs will be used to generalize the different parameters. It is therefore important that the key has heterogeneous parameters and that they are not similar to each other. Literature [32–34] has been reviewed on

Figure 6. Histogram of the QR code generated for image encryption within the framework of the European EyE project.

Figure 7. Histogram of the original and decrypted image.

how to value this type of attack, for which the key analysis has been calculated, and this parameter shown in equation (12) demonstrates that it is safe [21, 27, 35].

Figure 7 shows that the resolution of the decrypted image and original image is the same. The RGB histogram is the same on the three color channels and there is no significant difference between the original and decrypted image.

5.2. CIELab

On the other hand, the CIELab [36] space starts from a homogeneous space to assess whether there are more quantitative changes between the two images. This methodology has only been applied for dissolution, since this space is used to assess whether there are color differences.

Figure 8 shows that the CIELab coordinates of the original and the decrypted are the same. It can be seen in the sample that all points are distributed in the same way. Therefore, it is corroborated that there is no loss of resolution.

5.3. NPCR

The Number of Pixels Change Rate (NPCR) [37] is a metric used in image cryptography to measure the sensitivity of an encryption algorithm to small changes in the original image. Specifically, it measures the percentage of pixels that change their value when a single pixel in the original image is altered.

$$\text{NPCR} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^W \sum_{j=1}^H D(i, j)}{W \times H} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

This percentage is calculated in equation (9). Where W and H are the width and the height of the image and $D(i, j)$ is a function that determines if the pixel at position (i, j) has changed between the original encrypted image (C_1) and the modified encrypted image (C_2):

$$D(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } C_1(i, j) \neq C_2(i, j) \\ 0 & \text{if } C_1(i, j) = C_2(i, j) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

To compare this data, the Peppers.png image was analyzed to evaluate and compare it with other coding systems. An NPCR result of 0.9964 [5, 37–39] is considered sufficiently robust against threats. The resulting NPCR of this system is 99.6400%, which considering in terms of safety can be considered a robust system according to the literature.

5.4. UACI

The Unified Average Changing Intensity (UACI) [40] is a metric used in image cryptography to evaluate the average intensity of the changes in pixel values between two images: an original encrypted image and another encrypted image obtained after modifying a single pixel in the original image. This measures the average difference in pixel intensity and it is shown in equation (11).

$$\text{UACI} = \frac{1}{W \times H} \sum_{i=1}^W \sum_{j=1}^H \left| \frac{C_1(i, j) - C_2(i, j)}{255} \right| \times 100\% \quad (11)$$

To compare this data, the Peppers.png image was analyzed to evaluate and compare it with other coding systems. According to the literature [5, 40–42], a UACI greater than 30% is considered optimal for coding. In this case the result was 47.8000%, so this system could be considered robust.

Table 1. Comparison of results between AWS Lambda and Google Colab.

Architecture	Processing time	Cost
AWS Lambda	32 seconds	0.1336
Google Colab	1 hour 5 minutes	Free

5.5. Key space analysis

Given that the original keys include the 256-bit plaintext image hash value and the system parameters b and c , where b has 15 varied digits of decimal fraction and c has 14 varied digits of decimal fraction ($0.900000000000000 \leq c \leq 1$). The key space is the following:

$$2^{256} \times 10^{15} \times 10^{14} = 2^{352.35} \quad (12)$$

The result shown in equation (12) is greater than 2^{100} , therefore, according to the literature [21, 27, 35] consulted, it can be considered safe. Moreover, taking into account the extension of the keys, it can be considered sufficiently resistant to resist brute force attacks.

5.6. Computational analysis

In this study, we compared the performance and efficiency of two different architectures: a sequential system implemented on Google Colab and a distributed system on AWS Lambda serverless architecture.

In our distributed system on AWS Lambda, we found that the process of generating 1,000 QR codes, each carrying about 3,000 characters (totaling approximately 3 million characters), took an average of 32 seconds. This fast-processing speed is due to the concurrent execution of tasks that the serverless architecture allows. Furthermore, each Lambda function used about 250 MB of RAM for execution.

On the other hand, the sequential system in Google Colab took more than an hour to generate the same number of QR codes. This longer processing time is primarily due to the sequential execution of tasks. While Google Colab offers the advantage of free GPU resources, the inability to exploit task parallelization as AWS Lambda does can lead to slower processing times, especially for large datasets.

To estimate the cost of this process on AWS Lambda, we factored in the price of \$0.00001667 for every GB-second of execution and the fact that each Lambda function utilized 250 MB of RAM. The overall cost is computed as follows:

$$\text{Total Cost} = \text{Number of functions} \times \text{Execution Time} \quad (13)$$

$$\times \text{Cost per GB-second} \times \text{RAM Usage in GB} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Total Cost} = 1000 \times 32 \times 0.00001667 \times 0.25 = \$0.1336 \quad (15)$$

In contrast, the sequential system in Google Colab took over an hour to generate the same quantity of QR codes. Table 1 shows the processing time that stems mainly from the sequential execution of tasks. Although Google Colab proffers complimentary GPU resources, it cannot harness task parallelization in the vein of AWS Lambda, potentially resulting in slower processing times, especially for vast datasets.

Below is a comparative table of the outcomes achieved with both architectures.

6. Conclusion

During the development of this research, colorimetry and computation have been integrated in a joint way. For the development of the coding system using QR codes, methodologies related to multiplexing have been studied to know the state of the art. In addition, cases related to serverless technology have been studied. A methodology has been developed where the value of the alpha constant plays an important role in the development of the coding and a jump function has been added to improve it. To evaluate this coding system, two evaluations have been carried out, a colorimetric and a computational one. For the colorimetric one, it has been demonstrated by means of histogram and CIELab representation that the image resolution is maintained, and on the other hand, by the histogram, the robustness of the coding system has been demonstrated. On the other hand, the robustness of the system has been quantitatively evaluated by means of NPCR, UACI and key space analysis. These values demonstrate in a quantitative way the robustness of the system. Finally, serverless computing was compared with cloud and local computing for the execution of the same code. It has been shown that serverless technology optimizes the coding process. This research proposes an alternative for secure data encryption in different domains.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because no suitable repository exists for hosting data in this field of study. The data provided will be those shown in the article. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24455230.v1>.

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Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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